
Chemical Bonds in Interatomic and Intermolecular Interactions

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Abstract Theory of covalent and ionic bonds at binary interaction of complex atoms and molecular systems has been developed. It has been shown that a negative potential barrier occurs in the process of electron exchange and further increases the bonding energy of interacting particles. Quantum-mechanical substantiation of the origin of built-in electric moment in complex atoms and ions has been given which makes it possible to take into account correctly the electron-dipole and dipole-dipole bonds at binary interaction. It has been demonstrated how the molecules in gaseous phase, the clusters in condensed state, and close-packed state are formed. Model of the formation of negative electrons in atoms and molecular structures has been developed.

Keywords covalent bond, ionic bond, induced bond, electron-dipole bond, dipole-dipole bond, negative ions.

1. Introduction

At present, engineering and technologies are developed drastically at nano levels. At this level chemical bonds are fundamental ones. The energy resulting from interaction between individual atoms and molecules is determined by combined action of covalent, induced, ionic, electron-dipole and dipole-dipole bonds. Each of these bonds enjoys strict definition given at the level of concepts; however no consistent physical theory explaining bonds formation is available now. That is why it is impossible to perform computer simulation of strong chemical bonds between atoms and molecules in various aggregative states accompanied by the formation of complex molecular and cluster structures in gaseous and condensed states. In this connection, the following goal shall be set: to develop adequate theory explaining the creation of each chemical bond and their combined actions while forming diatomic and triatomic molecules as well as cluster structures and their interaction in condensed medium.

To reach the goal the following problems must be solved:

- to develop the theory of covalent bond between complex atoms in diatomic and triatomic molecules in gaseous phase and in condensed state;
- to substantiate the origin of induced bond between interacting complex particles;
- to develop the theory of ionic bond formation;
- to develop the theory of origin of built-in electric dipole moment in atoms and ions and, based on the theory, to determine the values of electron-dipole and dipole-dipole interactions;
- to consider binary interaction between atoms and molecules in close-packed state.

Let us consider, one after another, these problems.

Types of Chemical Bonds

Theory of Covalent Bond

Covalent bond is determined by the exchange of electrons between interacting particles. Each particle contains electrons in various energy states as shown in Figure 1. I -th and j -th energy states of particles A and B are

determined by ionization energy known for all atoms from periodic table [1,2]. Equilibrium positions r_e for many diatomic molecules are also known [2]. Distances r of the electrons from the center of the atom for the majority of atoms and ions are also known or can be calculated quantum mechanically.

Figure 1: Pattern of Binary Interaction between Two Particles with Covalent Bond Formation

For each pair of electrons of interacting atoms the exchange coupling is determined by means of the method developed by W. Heitler and F. London [3]. By solving Schrödinger equation for i -th stationary state of atom A and j -th stationary state of atom B the following energy of binary interaction was obtained [4]

$$W_{i,j} = \left(\frac{H_{1,1} + H_{1,2}}{1 + S} \right)_{i,j}, \quad (1)$$

where

$H_{1,1} = \iint \Psi_a^*(r_{a,1}) \Psi_b^*(r_{b,2}) \hat{H}' \Psi_a(r_{a,1}) \Psi_b(r_{b,2}) d\xi_1 d\xi_2$ is Coulomb integral;

$H_{1,2} = \iint \Psi_a^*(r_{a,2}) \Psi_b^*(r_{b,1}) \hat{H}' \Psi_a(r_{a,2}) \Psi_b(r_{b,1}) d\xi_1 d\xi_2$ is exchange integral, and

$S = \iint \Psi_a^*(r_{a,1}) \Psi_b^*(r_{b,2}) \Psi_a(r_{a,2}) \Psi_b(r_{b,1}) d\xi_1 d\xi_2$ is overlap integral.

Complete calculations of bipolar integrals have been

performed in quadratures [3,4].

Resulting wave function of binary interaction determines attracting forces and thus presents a symmetrical wave function of the following type:

$$\Phi_{a,b} = \Psi_{a,1} \Psi_{b,2} + \Psi_{a,2} \Psi_{b,1}, \quad (2)$$

Where indexes 1 and 2 relate to the valence electron of particles A and B, correspondingly. Each of these wave functions is represented by S-state for complex atomic systems

$$\psi_{A(B)} = \left(\frac{Z_A^*}{\pi n_A^*} \right)^{1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{Z_A^*}{n_A^*} r_{A(B)} \right). \quad (3)$$

Here $Z_A^* \cong \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_A \theta_i}{e^2}$ is the effective charge of i -th energy state with energy value of θ_i , r_A is the radius of

circular orbit of state θ_i and $n^* = \sqrt{W_H / \theta_i}$ is effective principal quantum number while W_H is the ionization energy of the hydrogen atom. Resulting energy of exchange interaction is as follows:

$$\bar{W}_k = \sum_i \sum_j W_{i,j}. \quad (4)$$

Obtained expression for covalent bond is applicable for interacting particles in gaseous phase. In case of condensed medium, the sums in (4) are substituted for appropriate integrals, then:

$$\overline{W}_k = \int_{(a)} \int_{(b)} \rho_{e,a}(\varepsilon) \rho_{e,b}(\varepsilon) \left(\frac{H_{1,1} + H_{1,2}}{1+S} \right)_{a,b} d\varepsilon_a d\varepsilon_b. \quad (5)$$

Here $\rho_{e,a}(\varepsilon)$, $\rho_{e,b}(\varepsilon)$ are distributions of volumetric electron energy density of atoms A and B, correspondingly, in condensed state.

At that, the integration shall be made from Fermi level to infinity [5,6] while Fermi level shall be determined from normality condition. The use of formulas (4) and (5) is restricted by two conditions: 1 – the calculations must be performed using different formulas depending on whether the energies of i -th and j -th states are equal or differ¹; 2 – wave function of each energy state is determined according to formula (3) with taking into account effective charge and effective principal quantum number.

Ionic Bond

At binary interaction of two equal particles or two different particles, the energy of ionic bond is as follows:

$$W_i = [(1 - P_a)P_b + P_a(1 - P_b)]S(1 - S) \frac{e^2}{4\pi\varepsilon_0 r_e}, \quad (6)$$

where P_1 and P_2 are probabilities that the valence electron will stay near the first and second interacting particles which are determined by the time electrons spent near each of the particle according to formula:

$$\tau_{a(b)} = \frac{2\pi r_{a(b)}}{v_{a(b)}}, \quad (7)$$

where $r_{a(b)}$ is the radius of the electron's orbit of particle (a) or (b); while $v_{a(b)}$ is the speed rotation around the

power center of particle (a) or (b), which is determined as follows: $v_{a(b)} = \frac{Z_{a(b)}^* e^2}{2\varepsilon_0 h g}$. Here $Z_{a(b)}^*$ is the effective

charge of power center of particle (a) or (b), e is electron charge, ε_0 is dielectric permittivity of vacuum, h is Planck's constant, and g is the statistical weight of the electron's circular orbit.

The times electrons spent near the first and the second interacting particles τ_a and τ_b are determined according to (7).

Then the probability of the event that both electrons stay near the first interaction particle is as follows:

$$P_a = \frac{\tau_a}{\tau_a + \tau_b} \left(1 - \frac{\tau_b}{\tau_a + \tau_b} \right), \quad (8)$$

while the probability they stay near the second particle is:

$$P_b = \frac{\tau_b}{\tau_a + \tau_b} \left(1 - \frac{\tau_a}{\tau_a + \tau_b} \right). \quad (9)$$

Induced bond²

This type of bond is determined by a potential barrier occurring between interacting particles when exchanging electrons. The electron when traveling from one particle to the other is partially reflected and retarded at the boundary interacting particles. Probability of such event is equal to product $P_1(1-S)$. At the same time the second electron is reflected from the boundary with the probability of $P_2(1-S)$. Developed electron density cloud contains the charge

¹ The border of change amounts to 0.1 to 0.4 units of $\sqrt{W_i/W_j}$, depending on the distance between power centers

² This energy was not considered in covalent bond before. Therefore, bonding energy of interacting particles was previously described pure qualitatively using various approximations.

$\Delta Q = P_1 P_2 (1 - S)^2 e$ which creates a negative barrier at the boundary. It is apparent that the part of particle flow overcomes the barrier at the boundary due to tunneling effect while the value of retarded charge is equal to:

$$\Delta Q = P_a P_b (1 - S)^2 (1 - D) e. \quad (10)$$

Here $D = \exp\left(-\frac{4\pi d_b}{h} \sqrt{2m_e d\varphi}\right)$ is potential barrier transmissivity, while $d_b = r_a + r_b - r_e$ is the width of

potential barrier, m_e is electron mass, $d\varphi = dqe / 4\pi\epsilon_0 r_{1,(2)}$ is Coulomb potential, $r_{1,(2)}$ the distance from the potential barrier to the center of the first or the second interacting particles, and S is overlap integral.

Developed induced charge interacts with the first and the second particles. As a result, an additional bonding energy occurs:

$$W_f = -\frac{\Delta Q}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{Z_a^* e}{r_1} + \frac{Z_b^* e}{r_2} \right), \quad (11)$$

where Z_a^* and Z_b^* are the effective charges of interacting particles A and B of single ions while $r_1 = 0,5(r_e + r_a - r_b)$ and $r_2 = 0,5(r_e - r_a + r_b)$ are the distances to the centers of interacting particles A and B while r_a и r_b are the radiuses of circular orbits of the first and the second interacting articles, correspondingly.

Developed electron-dipole and dipole-dipole bonds depend on mutual arrangement of the built-in electric dipole moments of interacting particles. Therefore, both types of the bonds for diatomic and triatomic molecules are different.

Electron-Dipole Bond

Arrangement of built-in electric dipole moment shown in Figure 2 occurs for each binary interaction as in this case the maximum overlap of the wave functions of interacting particles with their circular orbits takes place provided that every particle possesses a built-in electric dipole moment.

Built-in electric dipole moments occur in consequence of the deformation of spherically symmetrical internal S -envelope under the action of electrons of P -, D - or F -state. Method to calculate built-in electric dipole moments has been developed in [5] with taking into account Hund's rule. Verification of the developed method for the calculation of built-in electric dipole moments was performed through calculations of dissociation energies and ionization energies for diatomic molecules as these energies have been experimentally measured reliably enough. Molecules of nitrogen, oxygen, and carbon were taken as examples. Using above mentioned method, the internuclear distances and the built-in electric dipole moments were considered as variational parameters. Table 1 presents calculated values of the internuclear distances and the built-in electric dipole moments of the mentioned molecules. The difference between theoretical calculated values and those derived from dissociation energies and ionization energies does not exceed 5%. The calculated values of internuclear distances differ significantly from the average effective values derived from vibrational spectra. However, if the internuclear distances derived from vibrational spectra are used to

calculate the dissociation energies, then the overlap integral exceeds unity which fact contradicts its physical definition.

When a share of ionic bond occurs then one of the interacting particles features negative charge while the other one possesses positive charge. The presence of free excessive electrical charges both in the first interacting particle and in the second one results in the following electron-dipole bond:

Table 1: Values of Internuclear Distances and Built-in Electric Dipole Moments of Single Ions inside Molecule

Parameters	Molecules		
	O ₂	N ₂	C ₂
r_e (Å)	1.784	1.600	1.740
$P_{a,i}$ (C·m *10 ³⁰)	2.755/ 2645	2.613/ 2.723	1.976/ 1.895

$$W_{e-d} = 2P_a P_b (1-S) S \frac{e(p_{b,i} + p_{b,f})}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_e^2} + 2P_a P_b (1-S) S \frac{e(p_{a,i} + p_{a,f})}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_e^2}, \quad (12)$$

where $p_{a,i}$ and $p_{b,i}$ are built-in electric dipole moment of ions of interacting particles while $p_{a,f} = \Delta Q \cdot r_1$ and $p_{b,f} = \Delta Q \cdot r_2$.

In the process of exchange interaction between interacting particles, negative charge ΔQ determined above by equation (10) occurs. This negative charge interacts with dipole moments of the first and the second interacting particles weakening binary bond between the particles. Energy of this bond is as follows:

$$W'_{e-d} = 2 \frac{\Delta Q p_a}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_1^2} + 2 \frac{\Delta Q p_b}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_2^2}. \quad (13)$$

The presence of built-in electric dipole moments in interacting particles results in electron-dipole interaction with either positive or negative value. In the former case the binary bond is weakened but in the latter case, vice versa, the bond is strengthened. If dipole-dipole interaction exceeds electron-dipole one, then the built-in dipoles of interacting particles can arrange along one of the directions thus increasing bonding energy between particles.

Obtained bonding energies of binary interactions of atoms present the dissociation energies which mean bond breaking energies for complex molecular structures. Bonding energy of induced charge presents relatively small addition to the bonding energy of two interacting particles because of other types of interactions.

Dipole-Dipole Bond

This type of bond at binary interaction of complex particles is determined according to formula:

$$W_{d-d} = 2 \frac{p_a p_b}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_e^3}, \quad (14)$$

while the bond inside complex structure of interacting particles is determined according to [5]

$$W_{d-d} = \frac{p_a p_b \varphi(\alpha_i, N_i)}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_{e,\rho}^3}. \quad (15)$$

Here $r_{e,\rho}$ is the equilibrium distance in condensed phase determined from the value of the density of matter; $\varphi(\alpha_i, N_i)$ is functional binding resulting from mutual arrangement of electric dipoles in a cluster.

Thus, shaped electric field formed by the dipoles dictates necessity to take into account mutual arrangement of the dipoles which is determined by the structure of interacting particles.

In the process of binary interaction a particle with shared electron shell is formed due to sharing of outer electrons. Bond breaking energy for the newly formed particle is determined by all types of bonds combined. However, it is

essential to know the effective radiuses of interacting particles and equilibrium distances between them. Interaction at atomic level results in formation of diatomic and triatomic molecules as well as cluster structures; moreover, cluster structures can be formed not only by atoms but by diatomic or triatomic molecules as well. Therefore, atoms, diatomic and triatomic molecules present main particles to form one or another substance.

Figure 2: General Pattern of Diatomic Molecule

Formation of Molecular, Cluster and Close-Packed Structures

Formation of Diatomic Molecules

Figure 2 shows general pattern of the interaction of atoms in diatomic molecules. Such arrangement of built-in electric dipole moments takes place for all diatomic molecules as in this case the maximum overlap of the wave functions of interacting particles with their circular orbits takes place.

When considering successive arrangement of built-in electric dipoles of interacting particles in diatomic molecules it can be noted that covalent bond is sharply weakened because of decreased probability of electron exchange. In fact, it decreases twice which condition contradicts experimental data. Specific calculations of dissociation energies for diatomic molecules of oxygen, aluminum, iron, and silicon are presented in Table 2.

As soon as diatomic molecules formed, interactions of diatomic molecules with individual atoms resulting in formation of triatomic molecules start working.

Formation of Triatomic Molecules

Table 2: Values of Bonding Energy for Various Types of Interaction of Atomic Particles (eV), Internuclear Distances and Effective Radius of Molecules (Å)

Parameters	Interacting Particles				
	O+O \Rightarrow O ₂	Al+Al \Rightarrow Al ₂	Ti+Ti \Rightarrow Ti ₂	Fe+Fe \Rightarrow Fe ₂	Si+Si \Rightarrow Si ₂
r_e	1.784	2.78	3.070	2.604	2.349
W_k	-4.588	-1.095	-1.174	-4.742	-3.105
W_i	-0.465	-0.143	-0.110	-0.221	-0.346
W_f	-0.292	-0.177	-0.012	-0.407	$-4.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$
W_{e-d}	0.036	0.010	0.001	0.276	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-6}$
W_{d-d}	0.138	0.001	0.093	4.068	0.0415
\bar{W}	-5.120	-1.410	-1.200	-1.300	-3.409
r_{mb}	1.552	2.780	3.276	2.272	1.757

Triatomic molecule is formed through interaction of an atom with a diatomic molecule. Figure 3 shows such model.

Figure 3: General Pattern of Free Triatomic Molecule

The calculations of exchange energy, ionic and induced bonds for triatomic molecules are performed using the same formulas that applicable for calculations of dissociation energies of diatomic molecules while electron-dipole and dipole-dipole bonds are calculated according to individual formulas. In covalent bond, electron exchange results in formation of a negative potential barrier between interacting particles. Built-in electric dipole moments of a diatomic molecule are directed towards the area of the negative potential barrier. In the process of interaction of an atom with the diatomic molecule, its potential barrier keeps electric dipole moment of the atom directed towards the area of the negative potential barrier, as shown in Figure 3. Taking into account this condition, induced

charge in diatomic molecule ΔQ interacting with the dipole moment of the atom (Figure 3) weakens bond breaking energy while the charge induced between the atom and the molecule interacting with the dipole moments of the diatomic molecule in position of Figure 3, vice versa, somewhat increases bond breaking energy. As a result, bond breaking energy does not vary when changing position of dipole moments inside the diatomic molecule. The reason is that the collision of an atom with a diatomic molecule in gaseous phase occurs with the same probability both with its positive charge of built-in electric dipole moment and with negative one. Therefore, the formation of triatomic molecules in gaseous phase occurs with equal probability of the orientation of built-in electric dipole moments within the diatomic molecule: both in mutually opposite arrangement and in serial arrangement. Thus,

triatomic molecules feature allotropy in the arrangement of built-in electric dipole moments of initial atoms relative to each other.

In the process of substance transformation from gaseous state to condensed one, diatomic, triatomic, and polyatomic structures possessing shared electron shell are formed. Polyatomic formations present cluster structures. The sizes of cluster structures vary from some units to hundreds of nanometers. Nano structures were observed in regular water as fine ice crystals and were studied in great detailed in colloidal chemistry. However, at present time the nano levels of research, carried out in all areas of chemistry and physics are the most relevant ones. Such methods, in essence, mean cluster approach.

Nano Cluster Formed from Individual Atoms

Some atoms when transforming from gaseous state to condensed state form clusters. Cluster model of condensed state formed by individual atoms is strictly determined in [5,6]. In Liquids, particularly, short range ordering forms a cluster while free space between clusters contain initial particles of the substance which performs translational motions between clusters. Packing density of particles in the cluster corresponds to that of crystals: 0.68 to 0.74. Packing density of free particles of the substance in inter-cluster volume amounts to 0.44 to 0.47 [6].

Interaction of the central atom with the atoms of the first coordination sphere forms the cluster possessing the densest packing of particles and with the largest bonding energy. This cluster presents the main cluster containing 7 atoms in case of simple cubic arrangement; 9 atoms in case of **body-centered cubic arrangement** and 13 atoms in case of face-centered cubic arrangement. The main cluster when interacting with free atoms of inter-cluster volume can increase in size. Bonding energy of a free atom with the cluster is conditioned by the covalent bond and by the energy of physical adhesion determined by the electrons of the second and further ionizations with adjacent surrounding in the adhesion cell. Under low temperatures free atoms are absent in inter-cluster volume. Inter-cluster interaction makes the structure denser and each electron gets bonding energy caused by the covalent bond with all atoms of all three coordination spheres. In this case all substances, including metals, represent covalent crystals. A certain frozen state is formed which features dense packed clusters with disappearing inter-cluster boundaries owing to sharing the atoms of the third coordination sphere. Free space between clusters is absent. As a result, new 5-th aggregative state occurs: close-packed [7].

Nano Clusters Formed from Diatomic Molecules

Diatomic molecules form clusters with approximate form shown in Figure 4b. The clusters interacting with each other form a cluster lattice structure presented in Figure 4c.

Figure 4: Cluster and Cluster Lattice Structure Formed by Diatomic Molecules:
a – diatomic molecule; b – cluster; c – crystal lattice structure

Nano Clusters Consisting of Triatomic Molecules

In condensate state, when triatomic molecules interact with each other, their dipole moments in diatomic molecules are spontaneously arranged so that to ensure maximum bonding energy between molecules to form cluster structures. Such uncommon property of triatomic molecules makes possible forming cluster structures with maximum bonding energy as shown in Figure 5a. In Figure 5a, the molecules with serial arrangement of electric dipole moments within diatomic molecule are circled with dotted line. The bonding energy in such cluster in direct contact is determined by covalent and ionic bonds between the molecules and dipole-dipole bond between the atoms.

Figure 5: Cluster and Cluste Lattice Structure Formed by Triatomic Molecules Compared to Experiment: a – cluster; b – lattice structure and c – surface Si(111) [8]

When triatomic molecules interact with each other, the distance between the molecules is always smaller than their total covalent radius. Clusters in condensed state disintegrate under boiling-point. In this case, the energy of thermal motion is equal to the energy of binary interaction between the particles within the cluster.

Peculiarly, the clusters made from triatomic molecules in condensed state interact with each other in an unusual manner: they are engaged with each other in a way. As a result, a layer from triatomic is formed between central parts of clusters. Figure 5b shows the structure of clusters formed from triatomic molecules in crystalline state. Inter-cluster interaction is caused by the dipole-dipole bond only. Complete break of the cluster structure occurs at melting temperature.

Obtained theoretically cluster structure was verified experimentally using crystalline silicon (see Figure 5c) [9]. The agreement between the theory and the experiment is quite convincing.

Close-Packed State

As the temperature decreases, porous structure formed by the clusters becomes smooth, the cluster disappears and monolithic close-packed structure, predicted in [5], is formed. Experimental proof of smoothing cluster structures at low temperatures was presented and described in [10].

Artificially made close-packed structures are produced by applying surface active coating of atoms, molecules or clusters. In this case, first, gaps in inter-cluster structures of reinforcing materials are filled in, and further monolayers linked to each other by means of dipole-dipole interaction along the surface and transversely to the surface, as shown in Figure 6, are formed. As a result, the surface reinforced many-fold is achieved. Surface-active material of nano level on the solid surface of constructional material presents, in essence, new aggregative state with unusual physical-chemical, mechanical, thermal, electric, and magnetic properties [7].

The probability of formation of monolithic close-packed state is determined by the bonding energy of each substance particle with the particles of the third coordination sphere and is equal to:

$$W = \int_0^{E_{ce,3}} f(E,T)dE. \quad (16)$$

Figure 6: Close-Packed state: a) – of elongated molecules on **body-centered cubic structures** b) – of spherically symmetrical diatomic molecules 2 on sub-layer 1 of face-centered cubic structure with additional fillings of free gaps between molecules with individual atoms 3

Here $f(E,T)$ is Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution function while $E_{ce,3}$ is the bonding energy of binary interaction of the particles of the monolith with the particles of the third coordination sphere which was calculated for aluminum and turned to be equal to $2.30 \cdot 10^{-4}$ eV. If bonding energy is expressed in terms of temperature, then it corresponds to 2.67 K. Figure 7 shows the calculated values of integral (16) for aluminum depending on the temperature. Point T_C in Figure 7 marks the critical temperature at which superconductivity occurs. Then for aluminum at $T_C = 1178$ K the bonding energy shall equal to $1.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$ eV. The deviation from the calculated value of the bonding energy with the atoms of the third coordination sphere does not exceed 20% which is quite permissible for performed rough calculations of the energy of binary interactions for aluminum atoms.

Figure 7: Dependence of the Probability of Formation of Close-Packed State Versus Temperature for Aluminum

Close-packed state can occur at high temperatures as well. For instance, in case of plastic deformation the clusters possessing electric dipole moment arrange along one of the directions under the action of surface tension forces. Therefore, in near-surface layers the bonding energy per one particle increases by the value of electron-dipole and dipole-dipole interaction. The presence of such layer is particularly well observed in the deformation curves of brittle materials which feature mainly dipole-dipole interaction [5,6].

Formation of close-packed state on the surfaces of constructional materials results in considerably reduced frictional forces [11].

Conclusion

1. Have been developed: covalent, ionic, electron-dipole, and dipole-dipole bonds [5,6] and have predicted not known before induced bond [12] at interaction of complex atomic and molecular systems.
2. Has been developed: the theory of origin of built-in electric dipole moments in atoms and ions [6].
3. Has been developed: the adequate model of forming negative ions [13].
4. Has been developed: the model of formation of cluster structures [5,6].
5. Has been substantiated: close-packed state as the 5-th aggregative state of substances [7].

Using developed scientific basis there were predicted and experimentally verified a number of new phenomena. Hereby only the most significant of them are mentioned: 1. Formation of double electric layer near the surface of the solid when the solid is destroyed by means of convective and radiant heat transfer with high temperature of the electron component determined by the ionization with electron impact of negative ions. 2. Under high power radiant fluxes the rate of destruction of heat-shielding materials is reduced sharply due to the effective destruction of skin layer only. 3. In the frontal hemisphere of aircraft within Earth's atmosphere in transitional flow and free molecular flow a powerful violet-blue glow occurs (Gretchikhin's effect) [14]. 4. In cathode spots of arc and spark discharges a reverse current considerably exceeding the main electric discharge current occurs because of the ionization of negative ions [15], etc.

Complete substantiation have been made for: main concepts of forming nano technologies; methods of carbonic nanomaterials production; mechanical, thermal, emission, electric, magnetic, and photoelectric properties of nanomaterials.

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